

Studies on the Metal Concentrations of Bottom Sediments of the River Ganga

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Estuarine sediments are sinks of various pollutants transported from land. Both natural processes and man-made activities like rapid industrialisation enrich the sediments with trace elements. The trace metal concentrations in sediments serve as useful indicator for pollutional load carried by the river Ganga and its water quality.

Attempts have been made to study the trace metal mobilisation in sediments of the river Ganga at various depths at Kamarhati as well as along the banks of the river from Guptipara to Katchuberia, i.e. in the lower tidal zone. The metal mobilisation in terms of enrichment factor indicates considerable enrichment of the banks with trace elements.

Enormous amounts of nutrients like N and P and other exchangeable ions like Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} are being systematically deposited in the river banks^{1,2} (and bottoms) particularly in the deltaic regions. Many substances such as trace metals and nutrients may be mobilised as a result of natural processes like erosion, dissolution, precipitation etc. as well as man's activities and may thus become enriched in sediments³. Estuarine sediments are thus sinks for many materials transported from land. The sources of trace metal concentrations are silicates including a number of clay minerals together with metal oxides and sulphides. A rough estimate of the pollution load and sediment transport by the river Ganga to the sea has been documented⁴. The revised estimates of the pollutional loads in recent years are unknown even for water but the loads have been found to have increased considerably⁵. Naturally, it can be assumed that the trace metal concentrations have been systematically increased from industrial and other activities.

One of the most useful (but often neglected) management oriented types of investigations involves sediments. Sediments are reservoir for many pollutants including metals and monitoring sediment quality can give a long term cost-effective picture of pollution climate of water bodies⁶. Systematic monitoring of pollutional loads of the sediments of the river Ganga is yet to be undertaken. Monitoring of the pollution loads of the sediments of the river Ganga would provide additional information regarding the pollution load carried by the river. The metal concentrations may serve useful indicator for pollutional load carried by a particular river. Studies on estuarine sediments for trace metal concentrations have been widely reported in other countries^{1,6}, but no such studies are known for the bottom sediments of the river Ganga. However, NEERI⁷ conducted some sample testing of the bottom sediments in several stations of the Hooghly estuary for the study of trace metal concentrations, but the results are not of great importance. We, therefore, attempted to study the concentrations of some trace metals, namely Al, Cr, Cu, Zn, Pb, Ni, Hg in bottom sediments along the banks of the river

Ganga in a number of stations (including sediments from non-tidal zones like Patna) as well as at different depths with some samples collected from Kamarhati.

Water analysis only gives qualitative idea regarding metal ion concentrations. However, water analysis is based on grab samples and never gives the accurate and composite picture. The mean residence time of river water is only 12 days. It may be less for the Ganga. The metal contents vary from time to time and from segment to segment. The analysis of trace metal concentrations in deltaic sediments may provide a valuable information regarding the water quality of the Ganga. The study is also useful to find out trace metal mobilisation in sediments. The results are presented in this communication.

Results and Discussion

The results are given in Tables 1–3. Studies on the bottom sediments of the river Ganga at some selected stations and water intake points were made by NEERI⁷ during 1979–80. The results showed that the concentrations of the metals analysed are usually in the order of 10^{-5} g/g for Cu, Cr and Pb, and 10^{-6} – 10^{-7} g/g for Zn and Hg.

However, the results of the present study (on the basis of air-dry samples) show (in several cases) that usually the concentrations of Cu, Cr, Zn, Pb and Hg (where available) are in the order of 10^{-4} g/g, of Fe and Al are 10^{-2} – 10^{-3} g/g and 10^{-3} g/g.

The total chromium concentration at various depths increases with depth (except B-16) for samples of borehole B whereas it is more or less constant for samples of borehole-C. Fe concentration increases with depth, but Cu concentration is more or less constant with depth. Fluctuation was observed for Zn. The concentration of Ni increases with depth in sample B, but decreases with depth in sample C. Pb concentration shows fluctuation with depth but Hg remains even. The concentrations of metals in the sediments along the banks from Guptipara to Katchuberia show fluctuation. However, concentrations of Fe and Al in

TABLE 1—METAL CONCENTRATIONS (mg/g) OF SEDIMENTS FROM BOREHOLES IN THE GANGA RIVER BED NEAR KARMAHATI

Sampling no.*	Depth m	Al	Cr.	Fe	Cu	Zn	Ni	Pb	Hg
B-1	1.0	37.23	0.16	96.2	0.13	0.63	1.00	0.21	nil
B-13	19.65	24.2	0.18	152.0	0.13	0.71	1.12	0.36	nil
B-16	22.6–23.2	—	0.16	191.2	0.12	0.63	1.19	0.34	nil
B-21	30.75	21.25	0.31	208.9	0.12	0.53	1.19	0.36	nil
C-1	1.00	33.38	0.22	115.5	0.12	0.12	1.19	0.37	nil
C-4	7.5–7.65	18.88	0.22	192.6	0.15	0.62	1.06	0.35	nil
C-14	22.05	41.6	0.22	142.0	0.12	0.65	1.0	0.25	nil
C-20	30.1	37.71	0.24	208.9	0.12	0.58	0.87	0.49	nil

*B = About 30 m away from the bank, water depth 8.50 m from river bed levels; C = about 60 m away from the bank, water depth 10 m from river bed levels.

TABLE 2—METAL CONCENTRATIONS (mg/g) IN SEDIMENTS ALONG THE BANK OF THE RIVER GANGA

Station	Distance from sea* km	Depth, Position**	Al	Cr	Fe	Cu	Zn	Ni	Pb	Hg
Guptipara	191 R	—	—	0.20	100.4	0.09	0.16	0.40	0.21	0.35
Bandel	138 R	—	—	0.12	78.4	0.10	0.16	0.70	0.25	0.65
Dunlop	140 L	—	15.73	0.08	89.7	0.04	0.07	0.25	0.16	nil
Halisahar	138 L	—	16.02	0.07	78.3	0.06	0.17	0.55	0.12	0.55
Garifa	137 L	—	16.15	0.14	78.4	0.08	0.58	0.80	0.19	0.55
Hooghly	136 L	—	18.72	0.64	77.0	0.05	0.08	0.55	0.23	0.20
Naihati	136 L	—	25.87	0.20	97.0	0.20	0.82	0.55	0.12	0.45
Bhatpara	133 L	—	24.80	0.17	93.7	0.10	0.32	0.75	0.01	0.35
Uttarpara	103 L	—	—	0.17	85.4	0.14	0.15	0.75	0.25	0.55
Dhakshineswar	100 L	—	31.82	0.01	76.6	0.08	0.14	0.65	0.12	0.55
Baghbazar	97 L	—	27.17	0.12	72.1	0.52	0.13	0.60	0.15	0.15
Kakdwip	27 L	—	—	0.13	119.5	0.10	0.17	0.75	0.23	0.15
Kakdwip	27	3m, 50 ^a	—	0.07	99.2	—	0.03	0.75	0.22	0.15
Kachuberia	7 L	6m, 600 ^a	—	0.08	83.3	0.06	0.10	0.50	0.33	0.15
Diamond Harbour	47 L	9m, 500 ^a	22.0	0.08	90.5	0.05	0.15	0.50	0.12	—
Nariel Ghat	—	—	—	0.06	63.3	0.09	0.05	—	0.20	0.09
R.C. Ghat	Patna and nearby	—	—	0.12	60.6	0.07	0.09	—	0.09	0.35
B.K. Ghat	—	—	—	0.16	69.3	0.09	0.15	—	0.12	0.15
L.C.T. Ghat	—	—	—	0.10	18.8	0.02	0.15	—	0.14	0.35

*L = Left bank. R = right bank. ** (-) = On the bank; ^aaway from the bank.

TABLE 3—EF VALUES OF SEDIMENTS

Sample no./ Station	Cr	Fe	Cu	Zn	Ni	Pb	Hg
B-1	4.4	4.6	8.2	2.1	54.4	11.4	—
B-13	7.5	12.1	12.7	3.7	93.0	30.2	—
B-21	14.8	17.4	13.3	3.8	113.6	34.4	—
C-1	6.7	6.2	8.5	6.4	72.5	22.5	—
C-4	11.8	18.1	18.8	4.2	113.9	37.6	—
C-14	5.4	6.1	7.1	2.6	48.8	12.2	—
C-20	6.5	9.8	7.5	1.9	46.8	26.4	—
Dunlop	5.1	10.1	6.0	3.5	22.5	8.5	—
Halisahar	4.4	8.6	8.9	8.4	48.7	6.2	42915
Garifa	8.8	8.6	11.7	28.3	70.3	9.8	42570
Hooghly	34.6	7.3	6.3	3.4	41.7	10.26	13355
Naihati	7.8	6.6	18.3	25.0	30.2	3.8	21743
Bhatpara	1.9	6.7	9.5	10.2	42.9	0.34	17641
Dhakshineswar	0.3	4.3	5.9	3.5	29.0	3.1	5892
Baghbazar	4.5	4.7	45.3	3.8	31.3	4.6	6901
Diamond Harbour	3.7	7.3	5.4	5.4	32.3	4.5	—

several cases are significantly lower than those in samples B or C. Concentrations of Fe and Al in the sediment are fairly high. The concentrations of Hg, however, is quite considerable along the banks. It is appreciable at Dakshineswar (Wimco Match Factory and a number of major industries are located), Bandel (power station nearby), Halishahar (paper mill) and Bhatpara (paper mill, jute mill and other industries). The increased concentrations of the metal ions signal appreciable pollution of the water and this is particularly of great concern in view of their toxicity. The natural abundance of these metals in soils (in mg/kg)⁸ are Cr, 70; Cu, 30; Fe, 40000; Al, 71000; Zn, 90; Ni, 50; Pb, 35 (as contamination) and Hg, 0.06.

The enrichment or depletion of the elements in the sediments can be roughly estimated from the concentration factor (F_M) defined as $F_M = [M]_{\text{sediment}} / [M]_{\text{soil}}$. The data indicate considerable enrichment of the metal ions in the bottom sediments of the Ganga except for Fe and Al in some cases whereas Hg enrichment is exceptionally high.

It is to be noted that oxides of metals are concentrated in fly ash and bottom ash from coal combustion and smelters. They are carried by the rivers and deposited in sediments. Reductive dissolution of metal oxides of Mn, Fe, Co, Ni from trivalent to divalent states takes place under anaerobic condition. Moreover, dissolution of Co, Cu, Pb, Ni and Zn resulting from enzymatic dissolution of the metal oxides due to production of metabolites have also been reported⁹⁻¹¹. In natural ecosystems like sediments, sulphate-reducing bacteria is particularly important in the precipitation of sulphides under anoxic conditions¹². Organic matter mineralisation also takes place with the reduction of Fe^{III}¹³ and metal-organic compound formation may also take place. The reduction has a dramatic effect on the solubility and speciation of metals¹¹ and subsequent precipitation though the role of microorganism and microbial dissolution has not been studied in details. No microbial study of the Ganga sediments is known though some aspects of microbial dissolution of phosphorus has been carried out by Lahiri *et al.*¹⁴.

The enrichment of metal ions essentially arises from the reduction and subsequent precipitation of the metal ions. Dissolution of the metal ions on the other hand cause depletion of metals in sediments. The enrichment factor, however, can be better represented¹⁵ as

$$EF = \frac{[X]_{\text{sediment}}/[Al]_{\text{sediment}}}{[X]_{\text{fr}}/[Al]_{\text{fr}}}$$

where, $[X]_{\text{sediment}}$ is the average content or concentration of element $[X]$ in the sediment, $[X]_{\text{fr}}$ the average content or concentration of element $[X]$ in the surficial fresh rock, $[Al]_{\text{fr}}$ the average Al content in surficial fresh rock and $[Al]_{\text{sediment}}$ the average content or concentration of Al in the sediment.

Al is chosen as standard as it is poorly soluble and as yet not affected by pollution¹⁵. It is assumed that Al has reached a steady state at the continental surface, i.e. not at present being accumulated by the soil layer and is derived only from land erosion, a natural process. Natural processes of erosion would occur. However, this is not termed pollution. The enrichment factor can be estimated assuming

$$\frac{[X]_{\text{fr}}}{[Al]_{\text{fr}}} \approx \frac{[X]_{\text{soil}}}{[Al]_{\text{soil}}}$$

It is apparent that the concentration of Al at various depths are low compared to natural abundance but the Al content is still smaller along the banks indicating greater silica content in the bottom sediments along the banks. At various depths, adsorption and reaction of different metals with aluminosilicates in clays may be possible. Enrichment of Cr occurs at various depths at Kamarhati but enrichment is poor in bottom sediments. Similar to Al, the Fe content at various depths decreases possibly due to complex reactions of iron with various ions, microbial changes, etc. but in sediments along the banks, mud-containing iron in the colloidal state enhances the iron concentration. Enrichment of copper in bottom sediments is very high but less along the banks except at Baghbazar. The E.F. factors (Table 3) show considerable enrichment of Cr, Cu, Zn, Ni and Pb but depletion of Fe concentration at different depths. It has been found that the enrichment increases with depth for borehole-B. Slightly different trends were observed for borehole-C, the enrichment value at depth 22 m is always comparatively less. The enrichment of metals has been found to be maximum at 7-8 m whereas for Zn the values decrease continuously. The sediments along the banks show considerable enrichment of Cr, Fe, Cu, Zn, Ni, Pb and Hg. Iron can be regarded to be precipitated and coagulated at the bottom. However, at Baghbazar (near Calcutta) there is less enrichment. The enrichment of metal ions indicates greater metal mobilisation due to pollution or geochemical fractionation of certain elements in soil profiles or due to other reasons.

We are not in a position to calculate the transport of the elements by the rivers to the sea nor can we calculate the total pollutional load in absence of additional data regarding input from various sources. It is to be noted that sediments are in equilibrium with hypolimnion and exchange of metal ions is possible in a flowing river causing fluctuation in the concentration of metallic ions in the sediments along the banks and also in river water. Moreover, anaerobic microorganisms change the speciation of the metal ions which may affect the water quality of the river.

The data also give us a temporarily integrated picture of metal input. Moreover, the data are more reliable compared to those obtained from water analysis and can be used as index for water pollution.

Experimental

The samples collected were grouped in two categories : (i) samples at various depths at Kamarhati collected (1985-86) from the works carried out by Dadina Pvt. Ltd. in connection with the subsoil investigation work for the proposed intake jetty of Calcutta Metropolitan Development Authority at Kamarhati, and (ii) samples collected from the bottom sediments near the banks of the river from Guptipara to Katchuberia (1986-87) and samples collected from Patna. Sampling was made after 5–6 h of high tide so that the average and uniform samples between high tide and low tide were obtained. The samples were collected in polythene bags, soaked with filter paper and air-dried at room temperature. The data are usually averages from six samples collected from the place at a particular time.

The extraction of the metal ions from sediments and their estimation were made following the standard procedures¹⁶. The chemicals used in the extraction and preparation of standard solutions were of AnalaR G.R. (E. Merck) grade. Polished iron wire was used to prepare standard iron solution. Metal ions were estimated using a Varian AA-1474 atomic absorption spectrometer. Aluminium was estimated colorimetrically at 520 nm using aluminon reagent.

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